

**ARTICLES OF ASSOCIATION OF
HUMANITAS ARK**

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Preface

Science and technology is a double-edged sword, which can not only benefit mankind, but also destroy mankind. The stronger the ability to benefit mankind, the greater the power to destroy mankind, and this destructive power will eventually exterminate mankind.

For more than 200 years since the Industrial Revolution in the mid-18th century, science and technology has been in an accelerated state of development, and the further development of some technologies will have the ability to exterminate mankind. However, the greed, selfishness and shortsightedness of human nature drive the whole society to always ask for things immoderately from science and technology, and any warning to the harmfulness of science and technology is useless.

Mr. Hu Jiaqi, the founder of Humanitas Ark, has been studying human problems for 40 years, which is also a process of running, appealing and shouting, however, his own fight produced very little effect. He deeply feels that the end of human extinction is fast approaching, thus science and technology must be braked sharply, and the world must be unified as soon as possible to strictly restrict the development of science and technology. We humans urgently need the whole awakening and a force is urgently needed to promote a great awakening movement.

After deep consideration, Mr. Hu Jiaqi decided to establish Save Human Action Organization (now is officially renamed as Humanitas Ark, hereinafter referred to as the organization), and to use the collective strength of the organization to make every effort for the cause of saving mankind.

As the founder of the organization, Mr. Hu Jiaqi has done a great deal of theoretical preparation over the past four decades and formed his representative book "Saving Humanity", which provides a theoretical direction for all the work of the organization. In particular, he established three principles, namely, the maximum value principle, the justice principle and the far-reaching principle. These are not only the basic ideas of the organization, but also the universal theories guiding the practice of human society.

The organization holds that fully and properly spreading the existing safe and mature science and technology throughout the world can guarantee enough food and clothing of all mankind, so mankind must stop the greedy demand for science and technology immediately, and must strictly distinguish the research and development of each science and technology as a whole, for some science and technology that may pose a threat to human beings as a whole, especially scientific theories, they must be permanently sealed up, or even forgotten, so as to achieve the goal of restricting the development of science and technology in a unified way.

However, it is impossible to achieve this goal in today's society, because science and technology is the first productive force and is extremely attractive. The United Nations cannot control the behavior of countries because of their sovereign independence. In fact, the world is in the state of separate governance, no one can limit the development of science and technology for the benefit of mankind. Only by achieving great unification of mankind

with the power of world government, can we achieve the goal of strictly restricting the development of science and technology.

The organization believes that, although the realization of the great unification of mankind will touch the interests of many people, what interests are more important than the overall survival of mankind! From the recorded law of development of human history for thousands of years, it can be seen that the hard conditions that may really hinder the expansion of political entities can only be the inconvenience of transportation and communication, which leads to the ungovernability of a large country, and all the other obstacles can be overcome. Nowadays, the advanced transportation and communication have unified the world in a global village. What is needed to achieve the great unification of mankind is only a consensus- if the great unification is not achieved and the development of science and technology is not limited by the power of the world regime, the mankind will be extinct.

The organization believes that a united society is not only a society that can save humanity from extinction, but also an ideal society that can bring common well being to humanity. In today's society, there is a confrontational relationship between countries, which results in all countries mobilizing and driving all their elements forward to surpass their rivals. Therefore, today's human society is a highly competitive society, in which people live very tired and hard. At the same time, countries may use ethnic, religious and other contradictions to strengthen the power of this confrontation, which leads to frequent wars and terrorist killings due to the confrontation and contradictions between the countries, ethnic groups and religions. So people have a poor sense of security and well-being.

The great unification of mankind and the demise of the country means that the most powerful and competitive rival entity in the human world has disappeared. There is only one world government in the world, and without many supreme power bodies, there will be no confrontation and competition among many supreme power bodies. The world government only represents the interests of all mankind, and also just the interests of all mankind. Such a government will sincerely make the great unification society into the one that can best bring common well being to mankind, which is a peaceful, friendly and non-competitive society with equal wealth. The organization believes that under the guidance of this goal, the world government has the ability and motivation to formulate a series of national and religious integration policies, to promote a series of entirely new cultural ideas and moral values, and to adopt a series of economic and social management measures. Thus, there will be few wars, few terrorist killings, few fierce competitions, but peace and friendliness and universal prosperity in the world.

It should be emphasized that the great unity society will never become a poor society for restricting the development of science and technology, because the widespread of existing safe and mature science and technology to all parts of the world can guarantee enough food and clothing of all mankind. Today's rich countries are wealthier by making fuller use of these technologies; today's poor countries are poorer by not making full use of them. With the great unification of mankind, the world government will govern the whole world in a unified way and make it possible to spread widely the mature and safe scientific and technological achievements, which may be the basis of enough food and clothing as well as the basis of equal wealth. At the same time, because of the demise of the country, large military expenditures will be minimal; business and management costs arising from national barriers will be significantly reduced. This series of surplus costs can benefit every human being. Therefore, the great unity society is not only a society that can avoid human extinction, but also an ideal society that can bring common well being to mankind.

It is for this purpose that the Organization promotes an awakening movement for all humankind!

Chapter I General Provisions

Article 1 Nature

The organization is a non-governmental international organization whose mission is to save mankind from extinction.

Article 2 Purpose

The organization is devoted to promoting an awakening movement of all mankind in a peaceful manner, making all mankind recognize that the continuing development of science and technology is bound to exterminate mankind soon, and that only by achieving the great unification of mankind, adopting the power of world government and firmly restricting the development of science and technology can we save mankind from extinction. And make all mankind realize further that the great unity society is also the society that can bring universal happiness to all mankind. This is because the social form of great unification is particularly suitable to build human society into a peaceful, friendly and non-competitive society with equal wealth, in which the common well-being is the strongest. Our organization is engaged in the cause of all mankind, transcending the country, the nation, the party and ideology. Our Organization is wholeheartedly loyal to all mankind, and the focus of all interests and actions is only all mankind.

The ultimate goal of the organization is to achieve sustainable survival and common well being of mankind.

Article 3 Basic Concept

The three principles established by Mr. Hu Jiaqi are also the basic concept of the organization, namely:

1. The maximum value principle. The criterion of Humanitas Ark is as follows: we consider mankind as a whole (not specific individuals, groups or generations) and try to maximize the value of all mankind. In other words, survival, happiness, and other human values should be guaranteed for as many people as possible.

2. The justice principle. The organization will take realising the maximum value principle as a goal. The organization will formulate all systems, establish all structures and regulate all behaviors fairly and reasonably. This is also the justice that we believe in.

3. The far-reaching principle. The organization is devoted to the far-reaching, universal, and fundamental interests of mankind. It considers the fate and future of mankind and is dedicated to down-to-earth handling of every current affair that is concerned with human interests.

Article 4 Working Method

The whole survival of mankind is above all! For the sustainable survival and common well-being of mankind, the organization, with an open and cooperative attitude, is willing to accept all useful suggestions, to absorb all sincere people and groups, to dedicate all its warm blood and strength. The organization promotes its ideas globally through various means and ways to achieve its purpose.

The working method of our organization will strictly adhere to two principles: one is to strictly adhere to political neutrality, non-interference, non-participation, non-involvement and non-comment on national politics and disputes among countries; the other is to respect and strictly abide by the laws and regulations of all countries, and where countries do not allow the organization to carry out relevant work in their territories, the organization will not do so and will restrict the work of its members in that country.

Article 5 Oath of Admission

1. Taking an Oath

Before performing duties, leaders at all levels of the organization must take an oath before the emblem flag of the organization. Also, institutions at all levels must take an oath before the emblem flag of the organization as they hold important meetings. When taking the oath, everyone is required to watch the flag and clench the right fist before chest.

2. The Oath

I feel deeply that the irrational development of science and technology will soon wipe out human beings.

I feel deeply that the growth of material wealth has not brought universal happiness to mankind.

It is my will to join Humanitas Ark, to dedicate myself to the mighty torrent of saving human beings, and to be the hardest working droplet. I solemnly promise: I will observe the articles of the organization, and strive to perform tasks assigned by the organization. In order to ensure the sustainable survival of human beings and to bring universal happiness to all mankind, I will try to achieve the great unification of mankind in a peaceful way, and build a peaceful, friendly and non-competitive society with equal wealth. I will charge forward and never turn back!

Chapter II Membership

Article 6 Category of Membership

The membership of the organization is divided into two categories: individual members and group members.

Article 7 Conditions for Membership Application

Anyone who recognizes that the continuing development of science and technology is bound to soon exterminate mankind can apply for membership of the organization.

Article 8 Application Procedures and Approval

1. Application for membership:

Firstly: Generally submit the application for membership through the official website of the organization.

Secondly: if the official web is not accessible in some districts: 1) applications can be submitted by mail; 2) applications can be made in writing.

See the Annex for the relevant description.

2. For the applicant, the Board of Directors and the institution authorized by the Board of Directors shall issue the membership card upon review and approval, which shall normally be in electronic format and, in special cases, in paper format. Membership is granted from the date of receipt of the membership card.

Article 9 Standards for the Awareness Level of Membership

The means and approaches to ensure the sustainable survival and common well being of mankind need in-depth analysis in order to see clearly. The organization allows its members to have a process of learning and thinking, and divides the standards for the awareness level of membership, so as to help them raise awareness in a targeted manner and make reasonable appointments.

Level 1: Recognize that the continuing development of science and technology will soon exterminate mankind;

Level 2: Recognize that the development of science and technology must be restricted in order to solve the above problem;

Level 3: Recognize that in order to limit the development of science and technology, the great unification of mankind must be achieved, using the power of world government.

Level 4: Recognize that the great unity society is not only a society that can avoid human extinction, but also a society that can bring common well being to mankind.

When the level of awareness reaches the first level, it is possible to join the organization, but to be responsible at all levels requires a higher level of awareness.

Article 10 Rights of Members

Members enjoy the following rights:

1. The right to vote and to be elected;
2. The right to participate in the relevant activities of the organization;
3. The right to criticize and recommend the work of the organization;
4. The right to supervise the work of the organization and to keep it informed;
5. After the authorization and permission of the leading departments at all levels of the organization, the members may hold activities conforming to the purpose of the organization in the name of the members, and may apply for the guidance and assistance of the organization;

Article 11 Obligations of Members

Members shall undertake the following obligations:

1. Observe the articles of association and implement the resolutions of the organization;
2. Promptly publicize the purpose and concept of the organization;
3. Actively participate in the activities carried out and organized by the organization;
4. Safeguard the lawful rights and interests and reputation of the organization;
5. Do not use the name of the organization to engage in the work and activities that can only be carried out with the authorization of the organization;
6. Pay the membership fee according to the regulations (no membership fee is required at the initial stage of organization creation).

Article 12 Withdrawal and Removal of Membership

1. Membership withdrawal can be notified to the organization in writing and by e-mail, and the membership card shall be invalidated;

2. If a member commits a serious violation of the articles of association, the board of directors or a department authorized by the board of directors shall decide to remove the member from the list, and the membership card shall be invalidated.

Chapter III Organizational Structure

Article 13 Setup of Organizational Structure

1. The highest authority of the organization is the Global Members' Congress (GMC);
2. The highest decision-making body of the organization is the Council;
3. The highest daily affairs management body of the organization is the Secretariat;
4. Setting up branches at various levels under the supreme body;
5. The most primary body of the organization is the membership group;
6. The organization also has several honorary positions.

Chapter IV The Members' Congress

Article 14 Election of the Deputy to the Members' Congress

The deputy to the Members' Congress shall be elected by members through voting and subject to the one-man-one-vote system.

Article 15 Qualifications for Participation in the Members' Congress

The Members' Congress shall be divided into Congresses at various levels, and the deputy to the Members' Congress elected by the Members' Congress at the next lower level shall participate in the congress at the next higher level.

Article 16 The Supreme Members' Congress

The highest level of the members' congress is the Global Members' Congress.

Article 17 Rights and Responsibilities of the Members' Congress

1. Discuss the work report of daily management department and put forward corresponding suggestions;
2. Review financial expenditure reports;
3. Elect candidates in charge of the daily management department, two or three candidates shall be elected and awaited to be selected and appointed by the superior management department.
4. The GMC has the right to select directly the head of the highest decision-making body.

Chapter V The Council

Article 18 Composition of the Council

The council shall have a chairman, vice-chairmen and a number of directors.

Article 19 Chairman of the Council

The council shall be subject to the chairman-responsibility system. The chairman shall be assumed by the person who has obtained the most votes at the highest members' congress with the term of office of five years, and is allowed to get re-elected consecutively.

In the initial stage of the organization, the organization scale is small, not all regions have their deputies, the groups and regions represented are not extensive, the setting and operation of the organization is not perfect, so the chairman is assumed by the founder first.

Article 20 Vice-chairman and Directors

The vice-chairman and directors are nominated by the chairman and elected after obtaining more than a third of the votes of the GMC. In the initial stage of the organization, the vice-chairman and directors are appointed by the founders.

Article 21 Authorities and Responsibilities of the Council

1. The Council shall be responsible to the Supreme Members' Congress;
2. Decide when the Supreme Members' Congress starts;
3. Review the list of participants of the Supreme Members' Congress;
4. Decide the overall development direction of the organization;
5. Decide the plan of establishing organs and the appointment and removal of important personnel of the organization;
6. Supervise daily work of the Secretariat and other organs;
7. Appoint a Secretary-General of the Secretariat and approve the candidates for Under-Secretary-General according to the Secretary-General's proposal;
8. Review preliminarily the work report presented by the Secretariat to the Congress.

Chapter VI The Secretariat

Article 22 Composition of the Secretariat

The Secretariat shall consist of one Secretary-General and a number of Under-Secretaries-General.

Article 23 Secretary-General

The Secretary-General shall be nominated by the Chairman and elected by obtaining over half of votes from the Council.

Article 24 Under-Secretary-General

The Under-Secretary-General shall be nominated by the Secretary-General and approved by the Chairman.

Article 25 Authorities and Responsibilities of the Secretariat

1. The Secretariat is responsible to the Council and manages the daily affairs of the organization;
2. Put forward opinions on the candidates for the lower level of management body elected by the congress and appoint them with the consent of the Council;
3. With the consent of the Council, remove the unqualified or otherwise appointed person at the next level and reappoint the person in charge among the candidates. If there really is no suitable candidate, appoint the acting person in advance;
4. For the middle-level head, the Under-Secretary-General nominates the candidates and then the Secretary-General makes the final appointment. The appointment and removal should report to the Council for records.

Chapter VII Administrative Organs at All Levels

Article 26 Division of Organs at Various Levels

1. The most primary organ of the organization is a group of three or more members;
2. Above the group shall be a sub-branch under which there shall be 3 or more groups;
3. Above the sub-branch is the branch;
4. Above the branch is the regional headquarter;
5. Above the regional headquarter is the greater regional headquarter.

Article 27 Establishment and Cancellation of Groups and Sub-branches and the Appointment of Persons in Charge

1. As long as the number of persons is met, a group can be formed spontaneously. According to the one-person-one-vote system, one obtaining the majority of the votes will be the group leader and report the list of the group leader and members to the Secretariat by mail. After the organization is expanded, a group may also be formed at the request of the sub-branch. The group shall elect a candidate for the leader and report to the sub-branch for appointment.

2. As long as the number of groups is met, the sub-branch may be established spontaneously. The groups' representatives determine the weight according to the number of representatives and elect the head of the sub-branch (the sub-branch director), and then submit it to the Secretariat by mail. After the organization is expanded,

a sub-branch may be formed at the request of the branch. 2 or 3 candidates may be selected according to the aforesaid requirements, and submit the list to the superior organ for appointment.

Article 28 Establishment and Cancellation of Branches, Regional Headquarters and Greater Regional Headquarters, and Appointment of Directors

1. The establishment and cancellation of branches and regional headquarters shall be specially explained by the management institution at the next higher level, and be determined after being reported to and approved by the management institution at the next higher level;

2. The establishment and cancellation of greater regional headquarters shall be decided directly by the Council and directed by the Secretariat;

3. The persons in charge at all levels shall be elected from the two to three candidates selected by the organ at the next lower level and then appointed by the organ at the next higher level. The heads of greater regional headquarters are selected by the Council and appointed by the Secretariat.

Article 29 Removal of Persons in Charge

Institutions at the next higher level shall have the right to remove unqualified or otherwise appointed heads at the next lower level and reappoint heads from the candidates elected by the congress at the next lower level and, if there is no suitable candidate, appoint an acting head in advance.

Article 30 Honorary Positions

Honorary positions may be conferred upon persons who recognize the purpose and concept of the organization, have a great social power and have made outstanding contributions to the organization nominated by the Chairman and approval by the Council after their discussion.

Chapter VIII Management and Use of Funds and Assets

Article 31 Sources of Funds and Assets

The main sources of operating funds and assets include membership fees, legal social donations, legal fundraising, income from legal operations, interest on bank deposits and other legal incomes.

Article 32 Membership Fees

Membership fees are paid voluntarily by members and will not be refunded once paid.

Article 33 Use of Funds and Assets

The funds and assets of the organization may only be used for the development of the cause as prescribed in the present Articles of Association and the work related to the purpose of the organization. No entity or individual may embezzle, illegally divide and misappropriate them.

Article 34 Financial Management System

The organization will establish a strict financial management system, with a special financial department responsible for daily management, subject to the supervision of the members' congress, and disclose the financial status to the public in an appropriate manner when necessary.

Chapter IX Amendments to the Articles of Association

Article 35 Proposal of Amendments to the Articles of Association

1. The amendments to the general provisions of the articles of association shall be proposed by the chairman of the Council and submitted to the relevant departments for deliberation after being approved by the Council with more than half of the votes.

2. The amendment of the purpose of the articles of association may only be proposed by the founder of the organization or the person by written authorization of the founder of the organization, and shall be submitted to the relevant department for deliberations after being approved by the Council with more than two thirds of the votes.

Article 36 Effectiveness of the Amendments to Articles of Association

1. In the initial stage of the organization, amendments to the Articles of Association submitted by the Council shall take effect after they have been adopted by the Council, together with the Secretariat and globally elected representatives, with more than half of votes.

2. When the organization has grown and sufficient conditions are met, amendments to the Articles of Association submitted by the Council shall take effect after they have been adopted by the Global Congress with more than two thirds of the votes.

Chapter X Termination of the Organization

Article 37 Termination of the Organization

The organization will terminate due to:

1. The decision to terminate the organization shall be made upon the proposal of the Chairman, adoption by the Council with more than three-fourths of the votes, and that by the GMC with more than three quarters of the votes after submission.
2. Other irresistible factors cause forced termination of the organization.

Article 38 Liquidation of Property

Before the termination of the organization, a property liquidation group must be established. During the liquidation period, no activities other than liquidation shall be carried out. The remaining property after the termination of the organization shall be donated to the cause of public good related to the purpose of the organization under the supervision of the members' representatives and relevant authoritative notarial institutions.

Supplementary Provisions

Article 39 Effectiveness of Articles of Association

The Articles of Association shall enter into force on November 1, 2019.

Article 40 Right to Interpret the Articles of Association

The Council reserves the final right to interpret the Articles of Association.

Save Human Action Organization has officially changed its name to Humanitas Ark.

Annex:

Detailed description of the application for membership of the organization :

Firstly, the application is usually submitted through the official website of the organization, and the current official website is en.savinghuman.org. You could find the application for membership in the "Join Us" section of the official website.

Secondly, for regions where the official website is not accessible, applications can be made through the following two ways: 1) applications can be submitted by mail; 2) applications can be made in writing.

The current email address of application for membership of the organization is: join@savinghuman.org;

The postal address of the organization is: Room 2015, Times Fortune World, No.1 Hangfeng Road, Fengtai District, Beijing, China.

In case of any change in the official website, e-mail address and postal address, the members and the society shall be notified in a timely manner. Such change does not fall within the scope of change of the articles of association, and will be notified by the Secretariat with no need to go through the revision procedure of the articles of association.